

Historizing the Ancestral Kani Tribal Roots

Dr. S. Sushma Jenifer

(Former - ICSSR - Post Doctoral Research Fellow)
Principal, Maria Arts and Science College for Women
Valliyoor, Tamil Nadu, India

Abstract

Kanikkarān (kāikkāra) or Kani (kāi) is an isolated scheduled tribal community with unique physical, cultural, social, and tribal living stature residing in the Western Ghats of Tamil Nadu and Kerala. The present research, "Historizing the Ancestral Kani Tribal Roots", attempts to record the forgotten history of the Kani Tribe, which is on the verge of extinction. The present research is intended to document the historical traditions existing through orality of the Kani tribe, as they do not have a written form of language. Tribal discourses on the oral inscriptions of the Kani tribe decipher the latent ethnic-specific culture, tradition, myths and other rituals encrypted in the oral texts. The study's objectives are to map out the ethnographic history of the Kani people by deciphering the latent discourse and socio-linguistic concepts and grasping the different social, cultural and totemic aspects of the Kani tribe. It also enquires about the corpora of oral texts, decodes Kani's traditional messages and social discourse, and provides recommendations to the government and policymakers to restore the conventional and ethnographical means of the Kani tribes in Tamil Nadu and Kerala.

மலர்: 13

சிறப்பிதழ்: 2

மாதம்: செப்டம்பர்

வருடம்: 2025

P-ISSN: 2321-788X

E-ISSN: 2582-0397

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17311613>

Introduction

The Kanikkarān (kānikkāraṅ) or Kani (kāṅi) are a Scheduled Tribal community living in the rugged and mountainous Western Ghats regions of Tamil Nadu and Kerala. The Kani people, who inhabited Tamil Nadu and Kerala, knew they owned and guarded the Western Ghats. They are a Proto- Australoid minority tribe with a distinctive tribal culture that sets them apart from other people's perceptions and assumptions. The social construction of culture is how a society defines itself. It can be viewed as a predetermined way of living that defines a clan's or a person's identity. It is crucial to comprehend that the Kanikkar community's demographics can differ between these two states. The demography of Kanikkar in Tamil Nadu and Kerala is reported based on population, language, livelihood, and social structure.

Aim of the Study

The study aims to explore the Kani historical documentations and oral traditions that has been remained silent.

Objectives of the Study

The present study dwells on the Kanikkar's historical understanding. It determines to unearth the forgotten historical footsteps of the tribal Kani community.

Methodology

The research is based on the original oral descriptions collected from the Kani tribal people and the secondary sources of information. To illustrate the findings, secondary sources are gathered from the library, books, journals, papers, other online sources, and all the data are scrutinized.

Need for History

The word 'History' comes from the Greek term 'ἱστορία', historia, signifying 'inquiry or knowledge obtained through investigation'. It focuses on examining the past, especially as it pertains to human beings. History is recognized as an academic field that is used to tell a story, exploring and evaluating the order of past occurrences while objectively identifying the causative factors that shape them. Historians occasionally engage in discussions about the essence of history and its significance, contemplating the study of the field as a goal in its own right and as a means to offer alternative viewpoints on contemporary issues. Authors utilize history in their works as an inclusive term to connect past occurrences, the recollection, exploration, gathering, organization, display, and interpretation of information about those events. Events that took place before the advent of written records are referred to as 'prehistory'. The examination of history is deemed significant because it is through past experiences that individuals can learn how to navigate life appropriately. Notable authors have demonstrated remarkable skill in portraying life through the lens of history and literature.

Historical Background of Kani

The origin of the Kani settlement dates back to 4000 years, even before the Dravidian and the Aryan settlers. Kani enclaves are found in the dense forest of the Western Ghats at high-altitude hills that are aloof from the inland people. Shyam, in his research article

Aspects of Life and Language of Kanikkar Tribal Community of Kerala – A Study, addresses Kani as Proto-Australoid. Ethnographically, Kanikkar belongs to Proto-Australoid group. Some of them live in the interior parts of the forest, especially in the Podiyam, Mukkothivayal, Chonampara, Erumbiyad,

Pothod, and Plath regions in the Agathiyar and Kottur Forest ranges in the Nedumangad Taluk of Trivandrum district. Around 27 settlements are identified in these regions. (364)

Ershad Ali, in her research article Ethnic Composition of Indian Population, informs the Proto-Australoid as a group considered the second oldest racial group in India characterised by dolichocephalic head, broad and flat nose (platyrrhine nose) which is depressed at the root. They are further short in height, dark brown to nearly black in skin colour. The hair is wavy or curly. Supraorbital ridges are prominent. These features are found among almost all the tribes of Central and Southern India. (09)

A study on the Kani community culture reveals that their cultural practices have been responsible for enabling them to lead a good, meaningful, and dignified life associated with nature. Their living heritage has helped the community maintain its values, tradition, and identity, develop self-esteem, and survive adverse social and economic conditions.

Settlement History of Kani

Tribals are nomadic people with a migratory history that influenced their social and cultural aspects. Kani people lived in the wooded places of the Western Ghats for ages. They establish a close relationship with nature and depend upon the resources the area provides them for survival. The Kani is a semi-nomadic tribe that moved about the Western Ghats in search of food, water, and suitable habitats. They engaged in shifting cultivation, commonly described as slash-and-burn agriculture, which involves removing small portions of forest for cultivation before relocating to new locations after a few years. As the Kani people grew closer to the Western Ghats through time, they started to construct permanent settlements.

They acquired a thorough knowledge of the forests, their rich biodiversity, medicinal plants, and other resources. The Kani people have social and commercial relationships with the areas where the Malayalis of Kerala and the Tamils of Tamil Nadu reside. Language influences, cultural interactions, and social relationships contributed to the increased complexity and profundity of the

Kani community. When European colonial powers like the British entered India, it had a profound effect on the way of life of the Kani people. Their customary life methods were disrupted, and their ancestral lands were destroyed. When forests were declared reserved zones and boundaries were set for settlement, Kani's movement into the woods was restricted. Multiple theories highlight different versions of the migration history of the people. Stephen, in his book *Kokkarai: Life and Culture of the Kaanikaarar*, observes that the Kani people once lived to the west . . . on the Kerala side of South India's west coast - and they were forcibly sent to the mountain regions by Dravidians and Aryans (1). Ayyanar and Ignacimuthu, in their research article, *Traditional knowledge of Kani Tribals in Kouthalai of Tirunelveli Hills, Tamil Nadu, India*, claim that, "the Kani people may have come to the Tamil side through the Courtallam pass" (247). Tharmaraj, in his *Folklore of the Kani Tribe*, "perceives that Kani people once lived to the east . . . on the Tamil Plains . . . and migrated westward from Tirunelveli District through Kalakadu" (63).

Kani's legendary story about the Two Sisters claims that the Kani people migrated westward from Tirunelveli District. According to a legendary tale from ancient times, the Kani people lived on the plains of the east of the mountains. Two Sisters were living on the mountain. The elder sister had four sons, and the younger had three sons. These two groups of young men quarrelled, and as a result, the Kani people divided with the younger sister's children and went westward to the mountains to live in the forest. The elder sister's children went eastward to the Tamil coast to be a sea-fishing community (299). The forests and mountainous regions of Kerala and Tamil Nadu play a significant role in the migration history of the Kanikkar or Kani. The history of the Kani people's migration is the result of social, cultural, environmental, psychological and personal reasons.

Demography of Kani

Kani lives in Tirunelveli and Kanyakumari, the southern districts of Tamil Nadu. In Tamil Nadu, the Kani people are considered a small tribal group. Those who identify as Kani in Kerala are primarily located

in the eastern hilly regions of the state, specifically in the districts of Thiruvananthapuram, Kollam, and Pathanamthitta. Kani in Kerala is estimated to have a population of 5,000–7,000 individuals. The Kani tribe, sometimes known as Kanikkarans, inhabit large and small towns in or near forestland. In Tamil Nadu, there are 52 settlements, and in Kerala, there are around 70 settlements. Grace Varchese (2018), who investigated the sociocultural aspects of Kani, states:

Kannikars inhabit the hills of Neyyaattinkara and Nedumangadutaluks of Trivandrum district and also live in the adjoining district of Quilon / Kollam in Kerala state. They are short, long-necked, flaring nostrils, prognathous jaw and brachicephalic heads. Their colours vary from light to dark brown. Individuals of both sexes grow long hair and knot at the back of the head. (45-46)

Bourdillion's "Report on the Forest of Travancore" is a report on the socio-economic status of the Scheduled Tribes Development Department, prepared by the Government of Kerala in the year 2013, reports that, There are 5872 Kanikkar families spread over 48 local bodies in seven districts. As their population is 19455, the family size of the Kanikkar community is 3.31. The population consists of 9212 males and 10243 females. Therefore, the sex ratio is 1000:1112, which is higher than the Kerala state's average population. Kanikkar's community is mainly distributed in eight Grama Panchayaths in the Thiruvananthapuram and Kollam districts. (30)

The reports show the availability of a considerable population living in the Kani settlements on the Western Ghats of Tamil Nadu and Kerala. Krishna Iyer, in his book, *Travancore Tribes and Castes*, states that the "Kanikkar are a prominent group among the tribals in Kerala mostly found in the hills of Southern part of Kerala. They are the largest number of tribal people in Kerala (1). Adabiya, in her research article, "Culture and Traditions of Kanikkar in Kerala - An Analysis", addresses the Kani people as, "honest and truthful and are the sons of the jungle. Kanikkar can survive the challenges in the high terrains of deep forests and the dangerous wild animals (740).

The Kani tribe was previously a tiny nomadic, but now, it is a settled community. Most members cultivate mixed crops such as rubber, areca nut, banana, pepper, and cashew. Almost all the group members have small huts along with a small garden attached to them. The requirements on the tribal communities by the Forest Department have increased over the years, adversely affecting their ability to make decisions. They consider themselves the guardians and protectors of the forest. Their life, faith, beliefs, language, customs, religion, rituals, ceremonies, lifestyle, and emotions rest in their rustic forest environment. Their close association with the forest has made them as pure, innocent, and lively as the forest. The rich culture hidden in their community is also as secretive as the habitats of the woods.

Conclusion

The Kanikkaran, often referred to as the Kani, occupies a distinctive role within the cultural and demographic framework of the Western Ghats. As a Scheduled Tribal group with Proto-Australoid ancestry, their customs, economic activities, and societal structures set them apart from other groups, while simultaneously demonstrating profound connections to their natural surroundings. Understanding the differences in their demographic trends across Tamil Nadu and Kerala is crucial for appreciating their identity, resilience, and cultural preservation. This examination of the Kanikkaran people not only underscores their historical role as stewards of the Western Ghats but also highlights the necessity of safeguarding their heritage amid evolving social and environmental challenges.

Acknowledgment

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to the Indian Council of Social Science Research

(ICSSR), New Delhi, for their invaluable support and encouragement in carrying out this research work. The financial assistance and guidance provided by ICSSR have been instrumental in facilitating my study and enabling me to pursue this project with dedication and focus.

I also extend my heartfelt thanks to the ICSSR for fostering academic inquiry and creating opportunities for young researchers to explore, analyze, and contribute meaningfully to the field of social sciences. Without their generous support, this work would not have been possible.

Works Cited

1. Ayyanar, M., and S. Ignacimuthu. "Traditional Knowledge of Kani Tribals in Kouthalai of Tirunelveli Hills, Tamil Nadu, India." *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, vol. 10, no. 2, 2005, pp. 246–55.
2. Ali, Ershad. "Ethnic Composition of Indian Population." ZENODO, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2657332>.
3. Iyer, Krishna. *Travancore Tribes and Castes*. Government Press, Thiruvananthapuram, 2009.
4. Syam, S. K. "Aspects of Life and Language of Kanikkaran Tribal Community of Kerala – A Study." *Language in India*, Dec. 2017.
5. Stephen, G. *Kokkarai: Life and Culture of the Kaanikaarar*. Thinai Veliyiddu, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu, 1997.
6. Tharmaraj. *Folklore of the Kani Tribe*. South Indian Historical Documentation Publishing House, a division of Translingua Language Centre, Nagercoil, 2004.
7. Varghese, Grace. "Socio-Cultural Studies of Tribal Communities of Kerala." *Advance Research Journal of Multi-Disciplinary Discoveries*, vol. 24, no. 1, 2018, pp. 45–49.
- 8.